

COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION

GUIDELINES

Dissemination and communication efforts are essential for the success of SPATIAL by promoting the project's objectives, activities and achievements.

These guidelines will support such contributions.

[Internal communication](#)

[Website](#)

[Social media](#)

[Partners involved - social media profiles](#)

[Project in a nutshell](#)

[Newsletters](#)

[PR Material](#)

[Merchandising](#)

[Slide-deck](#)

[Participation in events](#)

[Technical & scientific publications](#)

[Open access repository](#)

[Branding](#)

[Imagery](#)

[EU logo & Disclaimer](#)

Blanca Arregui Communication Manager

To share your communication and dissemination updates and to address any question or doubts about the outreach activities or guidelines contact SPATIAL Communication Manager: Blanca Arregui (AUSTRALO) - blanca@australo.org.

INTERNAL COMMUNICATION

The main channel for internal communication are the [mailing lists](#) and the EMDESKplatform.

All information related to dissemination & communication activities will be shared in the mailing list referred to WP6 SPATIAL_WP6@groups.emdesk.com

At least one person per organisation should be registered and must attend the WP6 conference calls.

Direct contact: blanca@australo.org. Blanca Arregui will answer your questions/doubts related to dissemination and communication and she will redirect your questions, doubts, suggestions etc. to the entire consortium / the concerned partners, if needed

Other communication channels may include:

- **Zoom:** Consortium meetings will be held on Zoom. The WP Leader is in charge of setting up the meetings and sending invitations to the partners.
- **EMDESK Platform:** <https://spatial.emdesk.com/>. The coordinator will grant access to the platform upon request.

WEBSITE

SPATIAL website: www.spatial-h2020.eu

The project website:

- Gives a general overview of the project.
- Shares updates about the achievements, including news from solutions.
- Promotes the Community towards external stakeholders.

Each partner should actively contribute to populating the project website by sending periodic contributions to blanca@australo.org. An editorial calendar will be released in the coming weeks. Content can include:

- Presentation of partners and PIs.
- Participation in events, conferences, scientific publications, awards, etc.
- A brief recap of main scientific and technical achievements of the project.
- News related to a given WP/ Task.

SOCIAL MEDIA

Twitter account: [@SPATIAL_H2020](https://twitter.com/SPATIAL_H2020)

LinkedIn account: [company/spatial-h2020](https://www.linkedin.com/company/spatial-h2020)

Twitter

All partners are kindly invited to follow (via their company and/or personal accounts) the project's Twitter account.

Tweets related to any SPATIAL activity (e.g. meetings, events, news) must refer to [@SPATIAL_H2020](https://twitter.com/SPATIAL_H2020).

It is important to talk about the project in a concise, informal and positive way. Talk engagingly, and use hashtags where possible in:

- Clear and simple language
- Innovative and different
- Speak personally
- And don't be afraid to use humour to be entertaining.

The hashtags #AI #ArtificialIntelligence #MachineLearning #Cybersecurity should also be used.

LinkedIn

All partners are kindly invited to follow the [SPATIAL account](https://www.linkedin.com/company/spatial-h2020) to share and to comment on the posts published. In addition, if you find an interesting article or you publish something on LinkedIn related to the project, please, mention the project's LinkedIn page in your post.

PARTNERS INVOLVED- SOCIAL MEDIA PROFILES

THE PROJECT IN A NUTSHELL

The following text is a short description of the SPATIAL objectives and actions. It can be used in different contexts: emails, presentations, social media posts, etc.:

The **SPATIAL (Security and Privacy Accountable Technology Innovations, Algorithms, and machine Learning)** project seeks to address the challenges of black-box AI and data management in cybersecurity by designing and developing resilient accountable metrics, privacy-preserving methods, verification tools and system framework that will serve as critical building blocks to achieve trustworthy AI in security solutions.

The **main objectives** include: **1)** To develop systematic verification and validation software/hardware mechanisms that ensure AI transparency and explainability in security solution development; **2)** To develop system solutions, platforms, and standards that enhance resilience in the training and deployment of AI in decentralized, uncontrolled environments; **3)** To define effective and practical adoption and adaptation guidelines to ensure streamlined implementation of trustworthy AI solutions; **4)** To create an educational modules that provide

technical skills, ethical and socio-legal awareness to current and future AI engineers/developers to ensure the accountable development of security solutions; 5) To develop a communication framework that enables accountable and transparent understanding of AI applications for users, software developers and security service providers.

Besides technical measures, SPATIAL project aims to facilitate generating appropriate skills and education for AI security to strike a balance among technological complexity, societal complexity and value conflicts in AI deployment.

The project covers data privacy, resilience engineering, and legal-ethical accountability that are in line with EU top agenda to achieve trustworthy AI. In addition, the work carried out in SPATIAL on both social and technical aspects will serve as a stepping stone to establish an appropriate governance and regulatory framework for AI-driven security in Europe.

For more information: www.spatial-h2020.eu

NEWSLETTERS

In case your company/organisation/university is going to release a newsletter including information about SPATIAL], please inform the Communication Manager who can help you when it comes to present the project and its achievements.

Providing content for third parties newsletters is also recommended. Please, share with Blanca (blanca@australo.org) the third parties newsletters which could be of interest for the project. If you are contributing to some newsletters, please inform the AUSTRALO team at least one month prior to publication.

If you need any graphic or textual input to be used in the newsletter, you are kindly invited to contact blanca@australo.org

PR MATERIAL

SPATIAL material, logos and templates are available within the Project on the [Zenodo Repository](#)

The PR material will be available as e-documents, printing will occur as required (e.g. for events, workshops, etc.). AUSTRALO is in charge of this activity. All PR material whether in electronic or paper form (as well as videos) will use the specific project logo.

Mandatory in all PR material:

- SPATIAL Logo
- European Union emblem
- SPATIAL social media and website links
- Mention: “This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101021808.

MERCHANDISING

For any merchandising material that you have to print or produce, please contact the AUSTRALO team explaining your needs for production via email to miguel@australo.org

SLIDE-DECK

A slide-deck presenting the project in a nutshell, its objectives, activities and partners can be found [here](#).

This slide-deck can be used during your meetings/events while promoting the SPATIAL project. Please, use the pdf version when presenting.

PARTICIPATION IN EVENTS

A partner participating in an event with impact on SPATIAL should inform the Consortium and the communication team in advance (at least two weeks prior to the event, if possible) via the project mailing list in order to prepare a proper dissemination and communication campaign.

1. BEFORE THE EVENT

- Inform the communication team blanca@australo.org
- Report your participation in the SPATIAL table of events [here](#)
- Use [SPATIAL PPT template](#) if you are representing the project. If you are just mentioning the project in your presentation, you can use your company template but you must indicate that you are part of the SPATIAL and you must add the SPATIAL logo and the [EU Flag logo](#) with the acknowledgement “SPATIAL has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101021808.

2. DURING THE EVENT

- Tweet and mention [@SPATIAL-H2020](https://twitter.com/SPATIAL-H2020).

- In case you do not have a Twitter account, you should send the text you want to be published on Twitter and some pictures to blanca@australo.org. Please inform the Communication team about this need at least one week prior to the event

3. AFTER THE EVENT

- Prepare a blog post summarizing your participation in the event

Send the blog post to blanca@australo.org who will take care of publishing it on the SPATIAL website.

TECHNICAL & SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS

The technical and scientific dissemination plan is available in the [PROJECT REPOSITORY](#)

All partners are welcomed to identify and propose opportunities to publish technical outcomes (articles, workshops, congresses) and share them with the Project Coordinator. Once approved by the Project Coordinator, please, inform WP6 project manager Miguel García at miguel@australo.org.

OPEN ACCESS REPOSITORY

The SPATIAL Open Access repository is available at this [link](#).

Please, send to blanca@australo.org the papers, articles, scientific publications, blogs, etc you published in the context of the project. The project communication manager will publish it on [Zenodo](#), an open access repository.

BRANDING

The branding includes the fonts, colours, logos and banners that should be used in all project-related communication. Please find the Branding Guidelines [here](#).

Project name

The project name should be written IN CAPITAL LETTER (SPATIAL)
The full name of this is SPATIAL Project.

Font types to be used:

[FONT 1]: Use in **titles** - download it [here](#).

Exemple:

Open Sans Bold/Extrabold

Abcdefghijklmn

opqrstuvwxyz

1234567890

[FONT 2]: Use in **body text** - download it [here](#).

Exemple:

Lato Light/Regular

Abcdefghijklmn

opqrstuvwxyz

1234567890

NO OTHER FONTS ARE ALLOWED

Colour palette

Use colours from the dedicated palette:

These are the main colors to be used.

It can be used either with full saturation or at any lower level of saturation.

#042464 Should have the priority for longer texts and smaller ones.

 #049c9c

 #afdbdc

 #042464

 #586d97

Logo

Please find the **logo** available [here](#).

USAGE OF THE LOGO

As part of the project, you can use the logo in your communication and dissemination activity and material. Please follow the branding guidelines about the usage of the logo [here](#).

The logo of the SPATIAL must be visible in its entirety and placed on a background which does not compromise its integrity. The logo is unalterable and inseparable in all its component elements. Modifying the logo in any way is strictly prohibited. For reasons of integrity and visibility, it should always be surrounded by a clear space, or “protection area”, which no other element (text, image, drawing, figure...) can infringe upon.

If your company wants to add the logo to the website, please **link the logo** to the SPATIAL website.

The SPATIAL can be placed on your website footer, among your project’s credits or in the area where you list the funding institutions which supported you. Che

Please note that the logo must appear before any user interaction (click, scroll, input, etc.). The logo does not need to appear on pop-ups or redirected pages.

In case you want to add text, please find an example message to do so in [Logo, acknowledgement and disclaimer](#) at the bottom of the document.

Banners

Find the **banners** available [here](#).

IMAGERY

The best thing to avoid problems with the copyright of the images is to take some Creative Commons licensed images or Free for commercial use/No attribution required images from repositories.

1. **Created Commons licenses images** is a set of copyright licenses that offer the creator of a work an easy way to give the public permission to share and use their work under the terms and conditions of their choice. Creative Commons licenses are made up of four characteristics:

Attribution / (BY), requires the reference to the original author.

Share Alike / (SA), allows derivative works under the same or similar license.

Non-Commercial / (NC), obliges that the work is not used for commercial purposes.

No Derivative Works / (ND), does not allow you to modify the work in any way.

If you want to freely use free images for commercial use on your website / blog and you don't want to have legal problems, you can only use these two types of images:

- ➔ Images whose author has given you written permission.
- ➔ Images that have a Creative Commons 0 or CC0 License. The CC0 License indicates that they are public domain images and that you can freely use them for commercial use, modifying them and without the need to refer to their author.

2. **When using an image repository make sure that it says Free for commercial use / No attribution required**, like here:

Pixabay license: Free for commercial use / No attribution required, like here:

If you have doubts about the attribution or if the images fit with the topic, you can create a folder and insert the pictures to validate:

REPOSITORIES can help us provide nice and free images to use on social networks, blogs, etc.

- **GOOGLE images:**

[Google Advanced Image Search](#)

Google is a good place to start a search for images, since results will include photos from Flickr and other stock photography sites.

To start, go to Advanced Image Search. Fill in your keywords and specify the size, ratio, and other details as you wish.

At the end of the form, select the usage rights that apply. That's either "Creative commons licenses". Once you've found an image you like, click through to the page to double check the license.

- **Unsplash**

<https://unsplash.com/>

- **Gratisography**

<https://gratisography.com/>

- **Death to the Stock Photo**

<https://deathtothestockphoto.com/>

- **thestocks.im**

<http://thestocks.im/>

- reshot.com

<https://www.reshot.com/>

- ISO Republic

<https://isorepublic.com/>

- FOCA Stock

<https://focastock.com/>

- Pixabay

<https://pixabay.com/>

- Canva

<https://www.canva.com>

- Shotstash

<https://shotstash.com/>

- Piscopree

<https://picspree.com/en>

- Freephotos

<https://freephotos.cc/en>

- PicJumbo

<https://picjumbo.com/>

- Pexels

<https://www.pexels.com/es-es/>

- Barnimages

<https://barnimages.com/>

EU LOGO, ACKNOWLEDGEMENT & DISCLAIMER

Beneficiaries of EU funding shall use the European emblem in their communication to acknowledge the support received under EU programmes.

Please find the acknowledgement according to the guidelines. You can adjust the text depending on what you are handing over or presenting.

The flag of the European Union, featuring a circle of twelve gold stars on a blue background.	SPATIAL has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101021808.
---	---

For any document you have to hand over, please note that a **disclaimer** is needed. In law, a disclaimer is a statement denying responsibility intended to prevent civil liability arising for particular acts or omissions. "The content of this document does not represent the opinion of the European Union, and the European Union is not responsible for any use that might be made of such content".

For further information, please follow the **guidelines** (https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/use-emblem_en.pdf) on the use of the EU emblem in the context of EU funding and apply the **graphical rules** (<http://publications.europa.eu/code/en/en-5000100.htm>). The text can be displayed to the right, to the left, bottom or up, depending on your needs. There is a choice amongst several fonts to write the text.